

HARNESSING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE FOR THE TRANSFORMATION OF FOREIGN ECONOMIC ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation

This article explores the multifaceted role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the development of Uzbekistan's foreign economic activity. It examines the potential benefits and challenges AI poses for the nation's economy, including its influence on trade, job markets, and societal dynamics. The article provides insights into global AI trends and recommends actionable strategies for the government and stakeholders to harness AI effectively while mitigating risks.

Keywords:

❖ *Artificial intelligence, digital ecosystem, digital platforms, GDP, export, import, software products.*

Introduction.

The demand for innovations and artificial intelligence is growing rapidly in today's world. In response, countries across the globe are making significant strides toward adopting smart technologies and fostering the large-scale development of artificial intelligence. In Uzbekistan, this is reflected in the adoption of the “Digital Uzbekistan-2030” strategy [1], as outlined in Presidential Decree. This strategy prioritizes the development of the digital economy through measures such as aligning the introduction of modern information technologies in industrial enterprises with their technological modernization programs, automating and managing all stages of supply chains to reduce logistics and procurement expenses, gradually automating workplaces, robotizing production processes, and integrating artificial intelligence technologies, enhancing customer interaction mechanisms to boost trade and improve service quality.

The initiative also emphasizes updating the legal framework for e-commerce to align with international standards and enhance

information security measures. By 2027, the localization of software for automation, robotics, and artificial intelligence technologies is targeted, with hardware localization set for completion by 2030, supported by private partnerships.

Literature review.

AI has been extensively studied in the context of international trade and economic development. According to a report by the World Economic Forum (2022), AI-driven technologies, such as predictive analytics and automated trade processes, are revolutionizing global trade networks by reducing transaction costs and improving supply chain efficiency. Stanford University's Artificial Intelligence Index (2023) highlights the role of machine learning in optimizing market predictions and enhancing trade negotiations.

UNCTAD's 2023 report, AI for Trade and Development, emphasizes how AI applications are streamlining customs clearance processes and fostering cross-border e-commerce. Similarly, a study by OECD (2022) indicates

that AI-powered solutions are helping developing countries increase export competitiveness.

AI's impact on economic development is well-documented in works such as Brynjolfsson and McAfee's *The Second Machine Age* [2], which discusses how automation and AI drive productivity and growth. More recent studies, including a paper by Zheng [3], show how AI facilitates foreign direct investment (FDI) by identifying profitable ventures and streamlining investment processes.

Professor A. Abdugafarov [4] researches digitalization of the economy carried out in its initial stages and current directions of development the specific features that are being increased and the results that have been introduced are widely available

Research methodology.

In the article, the use of artificial intelligence to change foreign economic activity in Uzbekistan, some theoretical factors are schematized, and methods such as comparison, synthesis, and deduction are widely used.

Analysis and discussion of results.

Artificial intelligence (AI) has a significant impact on the modern economy, how companies conduct business, make decisions, and interact with customers changing relations. Its ever-increasing distribution and use to increase efficiency, improve service quality and opens up new opportunities to simplify operations. Artificial intelligence the main sectors that have a significant impact on the economy are finance, healthcare, manufacturing, retail and other sectors.

In Uzbekistan, too, through informatization and the development of the digital economy to take a place among the leading countries with innovative development by 2030 identified as a priority task.

"Digital economy and electronic on the measures of wide implementation of the

government" and "State social welfare for the population on the automation of procedures for providing services and assistance decisions on additional measures" and other regulatory legal documents acceleration of digitization in our country and socio-economic spheres aimed at introducing modern technologies [5].

It is known that modern artificial intelligence is designed to perform various actions consists of algorithms and software systems, and is one that the human mind can perform how many tasks it performs based on the information entered into the information base. Also, artificial intelligence deals with complex analysis and big data including programs, making logical and consistent judgments and making recommendations is a "smart" technology capable of Artificial by experts intelligence is considered as the basis of the fourth industrial revolution [6].

As a result of the introduction of artificial intelligence and other advanced technologies, in 2025 more than 430,000 new jobs can be created in two main sectors of Uzbekistan's industry by the end of the year. However, this only requires the implementation of country-supported policies and investment in skills and knowledge.

The modern AI landscape is focused on enhancing emotional intelligence, cognitive capabilities, and the ability of AI to effectively handle diverse situations. Deep learning plays a crucial role by enabling AI to acquire various skills and comprehend the physical world, while advancements in computing power and the proliferation of big data drive continuous improvements in AI algorithms.

Key AI Technological Trends for the Coming Years:

1. Development of Emotional Intelligence Technologies: Notable innovations include a polygraph-like system developed by the Canadian company Nuralogix, which utilizes transdermal optical imaging and machine learning to analyze facial blood flow and detect emotions.

2. Sequential Learning: Inspired by neuroscience research on animals, this technology emulates the brain's ability to retain connections from past experiences to acquire and apply new skills.

3. Reinforcement Learning: This approach goes beyond pattern recognition by enabling AI to discover novel and efficient methods for accomplishing tasks. Rather than merely predicting outcomes, AI acts to achieve objectives more quickly or effectively.

4. Transfer Learning: This method allows AI to learn with less data. For example, Uber's XP software requires only 150 examples to reach 98% accuracy in handwriting recognition, compared to the 700 examples needed by traditional systems.

China prioritizes rapid product development cycles and fostering a highly competitive AI ecosystem. A prime example is Baidu, which has steadily increased its research investment, dedicating 15% of revenue in 2015 and 21% in 2020.

1. Corporate Venture Capital: Between 2019 and 2020, the average annual growth rate of corporate venture capital in AI was 47%. The number of transactions rose from 211 to 437. Despite a slight global dip in AI activity in 2020, Asia's share of transactions grew from 36% to

38%. Leading countries in AI investment include China, the United States, and Japan, with Russia ranking 8th globally.

2. Increasing Computing Power: The exponential growth of big data and advancements in analytics have driven improvements in hardware. For instance, Google's fourth-generation TPU2, introduced in 2020, is nearly three times faster than its predecessor. Similarly, Intel's next-generation Keem Bay AI chip, slated for 2021, offers fivefold energy efficiency improvements in pattern recognition tasks.

3. Open-Source Collaborative Learning Platforms: New open-source platforms facilitate collaborative AI development, offering enhanced features compared to existing solutions.

4. Big Data Growth: According to IDC, the volume of big data is growing by 40% annually, with an expected total of 163 trillion gigabytes by 2025 [7].

Statistics show that in the period 2016-2021 years revenues of the global artificial intelligence market increased by 350%, from 3221.8 to 11283.76 million US dollars (Fig. 1). By 2025, revenue should rise to \$89,847.26 million [8].

Figure 1. Income from the global artificial intelligence market¹

¹<https://www.statista.com/statistics/607716/worldwide-artificial-intelligence-market-revenues>

The global artificial intelligence market is undergoing an era of unprecedented growth, as evidenced by the income trend from 2016 to 2025. With its transformative impact across industries and regions, AI is set to become one of the most influential technological advancements of the 21st century. To sustain this growth, stakeholders must focus on innovation, ethical practices, and fostering collaboration between governments, industries, and academia.

Additionally, AI and machine learning improve economic predictions, aiding policy-making in developing countries. Studies in Bangladesh use the autoregressive integrated moving average model (ARIMA) for forecasting GDP, while neural networks along with support vector regression (SVR) models in African countries enhance GDP growth predictions. "The information on the economy that developing countries may derive from AI and machine learning allows them to comprehend their economic setting and assist them in determining where to put assets and how they can derive sustainable development" as mentioned in the study. Advanced computational techniques provide accurate economic insights, informing better investment and development strategies.

AI uses in finance in developing nations especially in Uzbekistan. Fintech and fourth industrial revolution technologies enhance financial inclusion and sustainable development in developing countries by increasing access to affordable funding. However, challenges such as bias perpetuation and increased risks accompany these benefits. In India for instance, the adoption of Generative AI (GenAI) in banking improves customer engagement and operational efficiency but necessitates strategic reskilling of banking professionals.

Harnessing artificial intelligence (AI) presents Uzbekistan with significant opportunities to transform its foreign economic activity and drive overall economic and social

progress. AI has the potential to boost economic growth, enhance productivity, and open new markets within sectors critical to foreign trade, such as logistics, manufacturing, and digital services. By improving efficiency, reducing costs, and fostering innovation, AI can strengthen Uzbekistan's position in the global economy. However, challenges remain, including job displacement, ethical concerns, and inequalities that could arise from uneven AI adoption. Additionally, issues surrounding data privacy, security, and biases must be addressed to ensure equitable outcomes.

To fully capitalize on AI's potential in foreign economic activity, the government must focus on building the necessary talent pool and infrastructure. Investments in AI education and training programs are crucial to create a skilled workforce capable of supporting the development and application of AI technologies. Promoting collaboration among academia, industry, and government can accelerate innovation and drive the creation of AI solutions tailored to Uzbekistan's needs in global trade and economic partnerships. Ethical guidelines for AI usage should be prioritized to ensure that AI technologies benefit society as a whole, while mechanisms for monitoring their impact must be established to prevent negative consequences.

Uzbekistan's commitment to leveraging AI is evident in its strategies for digital transformation, workforce development, and regulatory advancements. However, overcoming challenges such as limited funding, a shortage of skilled professionals, and underdeveloped infrastructure will require collective action. Partnerships with the private sector, civil society, and international organizations can provide critical resources, expertise, and knowledge sharing to support these efforts.

Developing a comprehensive national AI legal framework is essential for guiding the ethical and responsible use of AI technologies.

This framework should include clear regulations, increased funding for AI research, and public-private partnerships to foster innovation. Data privacy and protection guidelines, as well as mechanisms to monitor the societal impact of AI, will ensure the alignment of AI development with national priorities. By addressing these areas and encouraging international collaboration, Uzbekistan can harness AI to transform its foreign economic activity, enhance global competitiveness, and improve the well-being of its citizens.

Conclusion and suggestions.

In summary, Uzbekistan's efforts to harness artificial intelligence highlight the government's commitment to transforming foreign economic activity and driving broader economic and social progress. Through the establishment of policy frameworks, prioritization of AI development, and the launch of initiatives supporting AI research and

innovation, the country aims to modernize and enhance its global economic interactions. However, challenges such as a shortage of AI expertise, limited funding, and underdeveloped infrastructure could hinder these efforts. Addressing these barriers is essential for fully realizing AI's potential in reshaping foreign economic activities while minimizing risks.

The successful integration of AI into Uzbekistan's foreign economic activity can unlock significant benefits, such as improving trade efficiency, expanding market access, and fostering innovation in export-oriented industries. To achieve this, it is critical to ensure AI technologies are implemented ethically and responsibly, with an emphasis on inclusivity and societal well-being. By encouraging collaboration between government bodies, the private sector, and international partners, Uzbekistan can position itself as a leader in leveraging AI to advance its foreign economic agenda and enhance its global economic presence.

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